

A Kinetic Study of Interaction of Nickel(II) with α -Aminopentanedioic-acid-5-amide, α -Amino- β -(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-propionic Acid and α -Amino- β -hydroxypropionic Acid

H. C. MALHOTRA* and AMITABH K. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 3 September 1987, revised 15 February 1988, accepted 25 April 1988

The kinetics of anation of Ni^{II} with α -aminopentanedioic-acid-5-amide, α -amino- β -(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)propionic acid and α -amino- β -hydroxypropionic acid have been investigated as a function of pH, concentration and temperature, using Aminco Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer. In the experimental pH range 6.26–7.27 all the incoming ligands exist in two equilibrium forms but it is only the monoanion form of ligands which is reactive. The rate constants k_{obs} have been resolved into specific rate constants k_1 and k_2 corresponding to zwitterion and monoanion interaction of ligands with metal, respectively, at temperatures 25 ± 0.05 , 30 ± 0.05 , 35 ± 0.05 and $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.100 M (KNO_3). The value of water exchange constant (k_w) along with the activation parameters has also been computed.

FAST reaction techniques have made possible the systematic study of metal complexation kinetics, which has received considerable attention due to wide range of processes, metals are involved in. The kinetics data thus obtained can yield information about the detailed mechanism by which the ligand enters the first coordination sphere of the metal ion.

Glutamine, tyrosine and serine are terminal part of certain proteins, nucleic acids and metallo-enzymes. Study of complexation reaction of these amino acids alone can provide useful information about the behaviour of these proteins, nucleic acids and metallo-enzymes. Keeping this in view a comprehensive kinetic study on interaction of Ni^{II} with glutamine, serine and tyrosine in the pH range 6.26–7.27 and at temperatures 25 ± 0.05 , 30 ± 0.05 , 35 ± 0.05 and $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$ have been carried out.

Experimental

α -Aminopentanedioic-acid-5-amide (glutamine; Sarabhai), α -amino- β -hydroxypropionic acid (serine; B.D.H.), α -amino- β -(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)propionic acid (tyrosine; B.D.H.), KNO_3 (Sarabhai, G.R.), bromothymol blue (AnalaR), $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (E. Merck) were used as such.

The pH was adjusted using 2, 6-lutidine (Merck Schuchardt) and HCl (Glaxo, A.R.) The final pH was taken on a Radiometer pHM 26 pH meter. The system was maintained at the desired temperature using immersion type thermostat (German model NBE).

Measurements: Kinetic measurements were made on a Aminco Morrow stopped-flow spectro-

photometer. The reactions were followed at 620 nm by pH indicator method¹ using bromothymol blue. All the reactions were carried out at ionic strength 0.1 M KNO_3 , neglecting the effect of metal ions (10^{-3} M) on ionic strength. All runs were made under pseudo-first order conditions using excess of metal ion over ligand. Blank experiments in which (i) indicator and metal solution and (ii) indicator and ligand solution were mixed showed no absorbance change at 620 nm to interfere with the results. The total absorbance change was kept small so that the relative voltage change (ΔV) could be observed on the oscilloscope.

Results

Interaction of Ni^{II} with all the three ligands follows the overall differential equation,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[M(II)]}{dt} = \frac{-d[L]}{dt} = k_{obs} [M(II)] [L]$$

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR Ni^{II} BY Ni^{II} -GLUTAMINE, -TYROSINE AND -SERINE INTERACTION AT DIFFERENT pH

$[Ni^{II}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$ M, [Glutamine] = 1.18×10^{-3} M,
[Serine] = 1.12×10^{-3} M, [Tyrosine] = 1.16×10^{-3} M
 $\mu = 0.100$ M (KNO_3) Temp. = $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Ni^{II} -serine		Ni^{II} -glutamine		Ni^{II} -tyrosine	
pH	k_{obs} $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	pH	k_{obs} $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	pH	k_{obs} $M^{-1}s^{-1}$
6.37	20.6	6.39	6.41	6.42	5.25
6.70	28.8	6.54	9.62	6.58	7.21
6.91	57.7	6.68	14.4	6.77	12.8
7.11	96.2	6.82	19.0	6.95	19.2
7.34	144.0	7.25	49.1	7.37	49.2

Since $[M(II)]$ is in large excess of $[L]$, $[M(II)]$ term can be absorbed in k_{obs} and rate equation can be rewritten as

$$\text{Rate} = k'_{obs}[L]$$

This was confirmed from the linear plots of k'_{obs} and concentration of the reactants. Second order rate constants k_{obs} were calculated (Table 1) using the relation, $k_{obs} = k'_{obs}/[M(II)]$.

The interaction can be considered through Scheme 1.

From the above Scheme it can be easily shown that

$$k_{obs} \frac{K_a^T + [H^+]}{[H^+]} = k_1^T + \frac{k_2^T K_a^T}{[H^+]}$$

A plot of $k_{obs}(K_a^T + [H^+])/[H^+]$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ is a straight line and k_1^T and k_2^T were evaluated from intercept and slope respectively (Table 2, Fig. 1).

a relatively longer side chain and an amide group in glutamine, a higher rate constant for comple-

Fig. 1. Plots of $k_{obs} \frac{K_a + [H^+]}{[H^+]}$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ for Ni^{II} -serine interaction.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k_1^T AND k_2^T AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR Ni^{II} -GLUTAMINE, -TYROSINE AND -SERINE INTERACTION

Temp. (±0.05)°C	Ni-glutamine		Ni-tyrosine		Ni-serine	
	k_1^T $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	k_2^T $\times 10^{-4} M^{-1}s^{-2}$	k_1^T $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	k_2^T $\times 10^{-3} M^{-1}s^{-1}$	k_1^T $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	k_2^T $\times 10^{-3} M^{-1}s^{-1}$
25	0.00	1.46	0.00	1.43	5.76	3.67
30	4.58	2.16	3.14	1.86	19.1	4.80
35	11.2	2.90	9.21	2.63	30.5	7.28
40	23.0	3.80	3.27	3.27	87.2	9.10
ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)		168		119		137
ΔS_1^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		306		146		215
ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)		43.8		46.5		50.2
ΔS_2^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		-86.4		-19.7		-71.8

The value of K_a^T (2.45×10^{-10}) was taken from literature³. At the temperature of our investigation, the corrected values of K_a^T were evaluated using the thermodynamic relation,

$$\log K_a^T = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{4.6} \cdot \frac{(T_2 - T_1)}{T_1 T_2} + \log K_a^{T_1}$$

The values of activation parameters are also reported in Table 2.

Considering the structure of serine, tyrosine and glutamine it is expected that the rates of complexation of serine and tyrosine with Ni^{II} would be comparable. This is in conformity with the observed values of k_1^T and k_2^T (Table 2). However, due to

zation would be expected and this is what is actually observed (Table 2). This is so because with the increase in length of alkyl group, its electron-releasing effect is also increased, resulting in favourable disposition of COOH group of glutamine to nickel and greater charge neutrality of Ni^{II} through chelation in comparison to serine and tyrosine.

Discussion

A general mechanism for complex formation involves a rapid ion formation between the metal ion and ligand, followed by the loss of a water

molecule from inner coordination sphere of the metal ion⁴ followed by an attack by the ligand (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The rate for this Scheme is

$$\frac{d}{dt} [ML^{(2-n)+}] = k_0 [(H_2O)_5 M(H_2O)L^{(2-n)+}]$$

$$= k_0 K_{0s} [M(H_2O)_6^{2+}] [L^{n-}]$$

Sound absorption and temperature jump⁵ data have been used to determine the value of k_0 . Utilising the expressions derived by Eigen⁵ on kinetic considerations, and Fuoss⁶ on statistical grounds, K_{0s} on theoretical grounds can be represented as

$$K_{0s} = \frac{4\pi N a^3}{3000} e^{-U(a)/RT}$$

$$\text{where, } U(a) = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 e^2}{a D} - \frac{Z_1 Z_2 e^2 K}{D(1+Ka)}$$

$$\text{and } K^2 = \frac{8\pi N e^3}{1000 D k_B T} \cdot \mu$$

where, a is distance of closest approach of two ions and other symbols have their usual significance. If the value⁷ of a is taken as 5 Å then the value of K_{0s} can be approximated to $1.98 M^{-1}$ at all temperatures of our investigation.

From Table 2 it can be seen that at all temperatures and for all ligands, k_1^T is negligibly small compared to k_2^T and it can be assumed that

$$k_1^T = k_0 K_{0s}$$

$$k_0 = k_2^T / K_{0s}$$

The value of k_0 and activation parameters are

reported in Table 3. The values of ΔH_0^\ddagger and ΔS_0^\ddagger compare well with the expected value⁸ of water exchange as determined for amino acids by temperature jump⁵ and sound absorption⁶ though our values have been evaluated using stopped-flow apparatus and give a better fit than earlier reported values.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF k_0 , ΔH_0^\ddagger AND ΔS_0^\ddagger FOR Ni-GLUTAMINE, -TYROSINE AND -SERINE INTERACTION

Temp. (+0.05) °C	Ni-glutamine k_0 $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	Ni-tyrosine k_0 $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	Ni-serine k_0 $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$
25	1.43	1.46	3.67
30	1.86	2.16	4.80
35	2.63	2.90	7.28
40	3.27	3.80	9.10
ΔH_0^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	40.4	46.4	5.71
ΔS_0^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-65.5	-25.8	-2.69

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A. K. J.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi, for award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. J. C. CASSATT and R. G. WILKINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 6045.
2. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Spec. Publ. No. 17 W 1, London, 1964.
3. J. E. LETTER and R. B. JORDAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2692.
4. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1969.
5. M. EIGEN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **1**, 176.
6. R. M. FUOSS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 5059.
7. BURGESS, "Metal Ions in Solutions", Hillwood, London, 1978.